

Speciation of binary complexes of L-glutamic acid with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in low dielectric media

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Abstract : Speciation of binary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with L-glutamic acid in (0–60% v/v) dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)-water mixture has been studied pH-metrically at a temperature of 303 K and at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹. The models for binary species contain ML, ML₂H₂, ML₂H and ML₂ for Co^{II}, ML, ML₂H₂ and ML₂ for Ni^{II} and MLH, ML₂H₂, ML₂H and ML₂ for Cu^{II}. The trend in the variation of stability constants with the mole fraction of DMSO was explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces. Distribution of the species with pH at different compositions of DMSO-water media was also presented.

Keywords : Binary complexes, stability constants, glutamic acid, speciation, DMSO.

Introduction

Speciation study of essential metal ion complexes is useful to understand the role played by the active site cavities in biological molecules and the bonding behavior of protein residues with the metal ion. Hence, the chemical speciation of biologically important ligands with some essential and toxic metal ions has been studied in this laboratory^{1–4}. L-Glutamic acid (Glu) is a ubiquitous amino acid present in many foods either in free form or in peptides and proteins⁵. Glu is the most important intra-cellular amino acid in many animals. It impairs neuronal calcium extrusion while reducing sodium gradient^{6–9}. Glutamate-induced intracellular calcium changes and neurotoxicity in cortical neurons *in vivo* was studied¹⁰. In brain, Glu is continuously released from nerve terminals during neuronal activity and has to be removed rapidly from the synaptic cleft to ensure uninhibited operation of the central nervous system. Glu acts as a neurotransmitter¹¹ and as a precursor of γ -aminobutyric acid^{12,13}. Hence a biomimetic study has been undertaken for Glu complexes of some essential metal ions, viz. Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, which are associated with several enzymes and any variation in their concentration leads to metabolic disorders^{14–16}.

Cobalt is an essential trace element for all multicellular organisms at the active center of coenzymes called

cobalamines. These include vitamin B₁₂ which is essential for mammals¹⁷. Nickel is an essential nutrient. It is a component of the enzyme, urease, present in a wide range of plant species^{18,19}. Copper is an essential element for life and one of the transition elements frequently found at the active sites of proteins. Metallic copper has antibacterial properties²⁰. Copper deficiency results anemia. Moreover, a congenital inability to excrete copper can result in toxic levels of copper accumulation, which leads to a metabolic disease known as Wilson's disease^{21,22}.

Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) is a dipolar aprotic solvent. Hence, speciation studies of the title systems have been undertaken based on their involvement in various physiological reactions. Protonation equilibria of L-glutamic acid and L-histidine in DMSO-water mixtures have already been studied in this laboratory²³.

Methodology :

Materials and methods :

0.05 mol L⁻¹ solution of L-glutamic acid (Merck, Germany) was prepared in triple distilled deionised water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid concentration to increase the solubility. DMSO (Qualigens, India) was used as received. Hydrochloric acid (Qualigens, India) of 0.2 mol L⁻¹ was prepared. Sodium chloride (Merck, India) of 2 mol L⁻¹ was prepared to maintain the

ionic strength in the titrant. Solutions of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chlorides (0.05 mol L^{-1}) were prepared by dissolving G.R. Grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L^{-1} acid (HCl) to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts. Sodium hydroxide (Merck, India) of 0.4 mol L^{-1} was prepared. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification²⁴. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method²⁵.

Procedure :

The titrimetric data were obtained by using calibrated ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01). The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred DMSO-water mixtures (0–60% v/v) containing inert electrolyte for several days. The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor²⁶. For the determination of stability constants of binary species, initially, strong acid was titrated against alkali at regular intervals to check the complete equilibration of the glass electrode. Then, the calomel electrode was refilled with DMSO-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. All the titrations were performed in medium containing varying concentrations of DMSO-water mixtures (0–60% v/v) pH metrically at $303.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ K}$. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1.0 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 cm^3 . Titrations with different metal-to-ligand ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75 and 1 : 5.0) were carried out with 0.4 mol L^{-1} sodium hydroxide.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD²⁷ was used to calculate the correction factor. By using pH metric titration data, the binary stability constants were calculated with the computer program MINQUAD75²⁸ which exploits the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of binary systems, the correction factor and protonation constants of Glu were fixed. The variation of stability constants with the dielec-

tric constant of the medium was analyzed on the basis of electrostatic/non-electrostatic, solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Results and discussion

The results of the best fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 1. Very low standard deviation in overall stability constants ($\log \beta$) signifies the precision of these constants. The small values of U (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ingredients at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems are validated by the residual analysis¹.

Residual analysis :

In data analysis with least squares methods, the residuals (the differences between the experimental data and the data simulated based on model parameters) are assumed to follow Gaussian or normal distribution. When the data are fit into the models, the residuals should ideally be equal to zero. If statistical measures of the residuals and the errors assumed in the models are not significantly different from each other, the model is said to be adequate. Further, a model is considered adequate only if the residuals do not show any trend. Respecting the hypothesis that the errors are random following normal distribution in the least squares analysis, the residuals are tested for normal distribution. Such tests are χ^2 , skewness, kurtosis and R -factor. These statistical parameters show that the best fit models portray the metal-ligand species in DMSO-water mixtures, as discussed below.

χ^2 distribution measures the probability of residuals forming a part of standard normal distribution with zero mean and unit standard deviation. If the χ^2 calculated is less than the table value, the model is accepted. Hamilton's R -factor ratio test is applied in complex equilibria to decide whether inclusion of more species in the model is necessary or not. The low crystallographic R -values given in Table 1 indicate the sufficiency of the model. The values of skewness recorded in Table 1 are between -1.23 and 0.81 for Co^{II} , -0.65 and 0.22 for Ni^{II} , 2.44 and 7.44 for Cu^{II} . These data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution and hence, least-squares method can be applied to the present data.

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}-Glu complexes in DMSO-water mixtures

% v/v of DMSO	log β mlh (SD)					pH-range	NP	U _{corr} × 10 ⁸	χ ²	Skewness	Kurtosis	R-factor
	110	111	120	121	122							
Co ^{II}												
0.0	4.53(29)		8.22(16)	16.82(35)	23.30(79)	5.0–10.0	28	0.09	18.10	-1.23	4.82	0.0095
10.0	4.68(36)		9.04(10)	17.33(25)	23.47(70)	5.0–10.0	28	0.07	3.62	0.81	2.90	0.0084
20.0	5.21(16)		9.39(8)	17.21(57)	23.92(43)	5.0–10.0	29	0.06	5.41	0.56	3.00	0.0075
30.0	5.44(27)		9.20(38)	17.67(99)	25.75(53)	6.4–10.0	18	0.63	3.19	-0.34	2.22	0.0075
40.0	5.35(16)		9.52(7)	17.64(40)	24.84(10)	5.0–10.0	34	0.05	7.18	0.00	3.89	0.0062
50.0	4.98(28)		9.17(17)	17.58(19)	24.68(89)	6.4–10.0	22	0.22	8.18	0.01	5.02	0.0140
60.0	5.51(22)		10.50(15)	18.43(24)	25.46(19)	5.0–10.0	42	0.04	16.3	0.15	3.66	0.0155
Ni ^{II}												
0.0	5.83(5)		10.33(7)		22.98(26)	3.5–8.5	43	0.07	7.99	-0.40	3.55	0.0065
10.0	5.95(6)		10.50(7)		23.28(37)	5.0–8.5	20	0.30	2.29	0.22	2.63	0.0051
20.0	6.03(3)		10.79(5)		23.40(29)	5.0–8.5	22	0.25	4.06	0.18	2.46	0.0045
30.0	5.92(4)		10.34(7)		24.20(12)	5.0–8.5	23	0.40	4.62	-0.02	2.61	0.0055
40.0	6.86(6)		11.78(10)		25.32(10)	5.0–8.5	28	0.11	4.00	-0.13	2.02	0.0093
50.0	6.63(3)		11.85(5)		25.11(7)	5.1–8.5	30	0.04	1.91	0.10	2.14	0.0056
60.0	7.02(3)		12.50(5)		25.92(4)	5.0–8.5	36	0.04	11.56	-0.65	5.42	0.0050
Cu ^{II}												
0.0		12.80(13)	15.30(8)	20.73(8)	24.95(17)	3.0–8.0	52	0.16	0.10	3.50	38.36	0.0094
10.0		13.00(7)	15.51(5)	21.07(4)	25.47(8)	3.0–8.0	52	0.06	0.01	3.93	11.08	0.0056
20.0		13.85(3)	16.56(3)	22.23(2)	26.73(3)	3.0–8.0	53	0.18	-0.04	3.91	11.42	0.0031
30.0		14.08(3)	16.12(5)	22.65(3)	27.10(6)	3.0–8.0	51	0.03	-1.15	7.74	19.92	0.0038
40.0		14.34(3)	16.20(5)	22.63(4)	27.52(6)	3.0–8.0	60	0.05	-0.13	2.55	14.84	0.0047
50.0		15.25(2)	17.23(3)	23.76(2)	28.88(3)	3.0–8.0	63	0.16	-0.60	4.89	14.89	0.0026
60.0		16.22(4)	18.49(7)	25.20(6)	30.54(6)	3.0–8.0	60	0.06	-0.15	2.44	20.00	0.0047

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(NP - m)$; NP = Number of points, m = number of stability constants; SD = standard deviation.

Kurtosis is a measure of the peakedness of the error distribution near a modal value. For an ideal normal distribution kurtosis value should be three (mesokurtic). If the calculated kurtosis is less than three, the peak of the error distribution curve is flat (platykurtic) and if the kurtosis is greater than three, the distribution shall have sharp peak (leptokurtic). The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic pattern in majority of the systems.

Effect of systematic errors on best fit model :

In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential parameters like concentrations of alkali, mineral acid, ligand, metal and volume (Table 2). The order of the ingredients that influence the

magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > ligand > metal > volume. Some species were even rejected when errors were introduced in the concentrations. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors confirm the appropriateness of the experimental conditions (concentrations of ingredients) and choice of the best fit models.

Effect of dielectric constant of medium :

The linear variation of stability constant (log β) values of complexes with variation of 1/D (D is the dielectric constant of the medium) of DMSO-water mixtures (Fig. 1) indicates that the dielectric constant or long range interactions are responsible for the stability trend.

Distribution diagrams :

Glu has two dissociable protons and one amino group which can associate with a proton. It exists as LH₃⁺ at

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on Ni-Glu complex stability constants in 60% v/v DMSO-water mixture

Ingredient	% Error	log β (SD)		
		ML	ML ₂	ML ₂ H ₂
Alkali	0	7.02(3)	12.50(5)	25.92(4)
	-5	4.96(17)	Rejected	Rejected
	-2	6.27(3)	10.90(7)	25.15(7)
	2	7.62(4)	13.78(5)	26.39(7)
	5	8.33(17)	15.38(21)	27.03(32)
Acid	-5	8.30(9)	14.97(12)	26.88(19)
	-2	7.57(3)	13.57(5)	26.36(5)
	2	6.43(2)	11.34(5)	25.28(6)
	5	5.50(9)	9.50(35)	Rejected
	-5	7.23(3)	13.09(4)	26.03(5)
Ligand	-2	7.11(2)	12.74(4)	25.96(4)
	2	6.93(3)	12.27(5)	25.87(4)
	5	6.76(3)	11.86(6)	25.79(4)
	-5	7.06(3)	12.67(4)	25.96(4)
	-2	7.04(2)	12.57(4)	25.93(4)
Metal	2	7.00(2)	12.43(4)	25.90(4)
	5	6.97(2)	12.33(4)	25.88(4)
	-5	7.00(2)	12.46(4)	25.87(4)
	-2	7.01(2)	12.48(4)	25.90(4)
	2	7.03(2)	12.51(4)	25.93(4)
Volume	5	7.04(2)	12.54(4)	25.95(4)

low pH and gets deprotonated with the formation of LH₂, LH⁻ and L²⁻ successively with increase in pH, in the pH ranges 2.0–6.0, 3.0–11.0 and above 8.0, respectively. Hence, the plausible binary metal-ligand complexes can be predicted from these data. The present investigation reveals the existence of ML, ML₂H₂, ML₂H and ML₂ for Co^{II}; ML, ML₂H₂ and ML₂ for Ni^{II} and MLH, ML₂H₂, ML₂H and ML₂ for Cu^{II}. The formation of various binary complex species is shown in the following equilibria.

The probable species in the pH range of study 4.0–10.0 are ML, ML₂, ML₂H and ML₂H₂ for Co-Glu system. At lower pH, the formation of ML₂H₂ predominates (Equilibrium 1). As the pH increases, the percentages of ML₂H and ML₂ gradually increase up to a pH of 10.0 with successive deprotonation of ML₂H₂ (Equilibria 2 and 3). In the case of Ni-Glu the species refined are ML₂H₂, ML₂ and ML. The formation of ML₂H₂ pre-

Fig. 1. Variation of stability constant values of metal-Glu complexes with reciprocal of dielectric constant (1/D) of DMSO-water mixture : (A) Co^{II}, (B) Ni^{II}, (C) Cu^{II}, (□) log β_{ML}, (▽) log β_{MLH}, (○) log β_{ML₂}, (Δ) log β_{ML₂H}, (◇) log β_{ML₂H₂}.

dominates at lower pH as in case of Co-Glu complex. Due to instability of ML_2H_2 , quickly it deprotonates to form ML_2 species (Equilibrium 4). The species ML increases with the pH (Equilibrium 10). All these species of Ni^{II} are formed below a pH of 6.0.

The species formed are ML_2H_2 , ML_2H , MLH and ML_2 for Cu-Glu system (Fig. 2). The protonated species were found to be predominant at lower pH. Fig. 2 suggests that MLH is formed through Equilibrium 5 but not

Fig. 2. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of Glu in 30% v/v DMSO-water mixture Cu^{II} .

through Equilibrium 6 because the concentrations of free metal ion and LH_3^+ are decreasing while the concentrations of MLH is increased. In the same pH region, the concentrations of MLH and LH_2 are passing through maximum simultaneously, which indicates that MLH cannot be formed from LH_2 (Equilibrium 6). Simultaneous formation of MLH and ML_2H_2 supports Equilibrium 1 for the formation of ML_2H_2 but not through Equilibria 7 and 8. As the percentages of MLH and ML_2H_2 decrease with increasing pH, the percentage of ML_2H increases up to a pH of around 5.5. Hence ML_2H should have formed through Equilibria 2 and 9. At higher pH of about 6.0, the percentage of ML_2 is predominant, may be due to Equilibria 3, 4 and 11.

Conclusions :

The following conclusions have been drawn from the modeling studies of the speciation of binary complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with Glu in DMSO-water mixture.

(i) L-Glutamic acid forms both protonated and unprotonated complexes under the pH of 3.0–10.0.

(ii) The binary species detected are CoL , CoL_2 , CoL_2H , CoL_2H_2 , NiL , NiL_2 , NiL_2H_2 , CuLH , CuL_2 , CuL_2H and CuL_2H_2 . These models are validated by statistical treatment of data.

(iii) The linear variation of stability constants as a function of dielectric constant of the medium indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces.

(iv) The charge on the species decreases, the species will stabilise in nonpolar solvent i.e. stability constant value increases with increase in $1/D$ (decrease in dielectric constant).

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